

Towards Culture-Aware Intelligent Systems

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Abstract—Understanding how the data used to train intelligent systems affects their behavior is a critical task in the artificial intelligence field.

It is also known that making robots capable to adapt their actions according to the culture improves their interaction with humans. For this reason, it may be crucial to know how the cultural component inside data affects the prediction of intelligent systems.

In this paper, we propose a method to acknowledge the cultural factor inside data and we show some preliminary results obtained by using a Random Forest model on two publicly available Datasets.

Index Terms—Culture-Aware, Artificial Intelligence, Intelligent Systems

I. INTRODUCTION

Intelligent systems are a technology that has grown in the last few years. According to a recent definition [1]: “an intelligent system operates in an environment with other agents, possesses cognitive capabilities such as perception, action control, deliberative reasoning or language, follows principles of behavior based on rationality and social norms, and can adapt by learning.”. A key goal of an intelligent system is therefore to interact with other agents (e.g. humans) by exploiting its capabilities. On the other side, it is well known that culture is an important factor that has to be taken into account during the interaction [2]. If we consider for example the thumb-up gesture, we notice that this is a widely recognized sign of approval in a lot of nations, but it is also used as an insulting gesture in Bangladesh.

By combining the two concepts of intelligent systems and culture, we propose a methodology for understanding the role of culture when intelligent systems need to be trained to perform a given task, for example classification. As an example, think about a system for activity recognition: recognizing a sleeping person may require different datasets depending on whether a person sleeps in a bed in a western house or a futon in a traditional Japanese house. The problem of using cultural information with intelligent systems has been recently addressed by some researchers, e.g. [3] developed a model for automatically adapting HCI systems to users using a culturally-aware adaptive procedure, [4] developed a method for generating culture-aware co-speech gestures, while [5] built a system that can be integrated into social robots for applying

an understanding of the culture, customs, and etiquette of the person which is interacting with the robot while autonomously reconfiguring the way of acting and speaking of it. Our method starts from the conjecture that, in a classification problem, the data to be classified are necessarily affected by cultural aspects. This method can be in principle used with any dataset containing a feature that clearly identifies the cultural context where data have been collected.

In the following chapter, we show some preliminary results obtained by relying on a custom Random Forest model with two different culturally-dependent datasets.

II. METHODOLOGY

The goal of the proposed work is to analyze how the cultural component affects the data by evaluating a learning model trained on different datasets. More in detail, we identified two public datasets [6] and [7]. In both datasets, we identify a feature identifying the culture x_c inside the data sample $x \in \mathcal{X} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^d$ used to predict output $y \in \mathcal{Y} \subseteq \{\pm 1\}$, where d is the number of features. During each test, we focused on a subset of the possible cultures to perform pairwise comparisons (e.g., Italian vs. Chinese or Jamaican vs. German), and therefore we extracted a set of samples and features for each dataset to be considered for classification. Specifically, we started choosing two admissible values a, b for the cultural identifier x_c , and we considered only the samples for which $x_c \in \{a, b\}$.

At the end of this process, we considered the following datasets:

- The CROCUFID food dataset [6] has the area of origin of the food as the cultural identifier with values $\{Asian, Western\}$, the domain $\mathcal{X} = \{22 \text{ visual features that describe the food}\}$, and the prediction $\mathcal{Y} = \{the \text{ food is sweet or savoury}\}$. That is, starting from the visual appearance of a food, we aim to predict if the food will be sweet or savoury, and we expect this depends on cultural aspects.
- The whats-cooking recipes dataset [7] has the type of cuisine as the cultural identifier, the domain $\mathcal{X} = \{58 \text{ ingredients that may be present/absent in the dish}\}$, $\mathcal{Y} = \{presence/absence \text{ of a critical ingredient for the person's health, e.g., sugar, butter, ingredient to which the person is allergic}\}$. That is, starting from known ingredients, we

Fig. 1. ROC plots of the whats-cooking dataset trained and tested with data coming from Thai and Cajun-creole cuisine. In each plot there is also shown the Area Under the Curve value as well as its average and standard deviation values computed on 500 bootstrap data samples.

aim to predict if a critical ingredient may be present or not, and we expect this depends on cultural aspects.

We trained and optimized four different Random Forest models:

- 1) It is trained by using only the data that have $x_c = a$ and by removing the cultural identifier.
- 2) It is trained by using only the data that have $x_c = b$ and by removing the cultural identifier.
- 3) It is trained by using all the data and by removing the cultural identifier.
- 4) It is trained by using all the data.

To choose the best Random Forest model we used 1000 trees and we optimized only the hyperparameter that controls the cardinality of the random subset of features that each node of the trees can check. We used 10-fold cross-validation and balanced-accuracy as well as AUC value as metrics. After the training, we tested each model by using two different test sets: one contains only data that have $x_c = a$ while the other contains only data that have $x_c = b$. To better compare the models we maintained constant the number of training and validation samples that we used.

The ROC curves with AUC values achieved by predicting if there is sugar or not in the whats-cooking dataset are shown in Figure 1: it can be noticed that models trained with data from one cuisine fail to predict the right class if tested with the data of the other cuisine. It can be also noticed that adding the cuisine feature in the model trained with all the data slightly improves the result but not significantly. This fact is also confirmed by analyzing the confusion matrices. By doing tests with other cuisines and making different predictions we obtained results that are not always coherent with the one

presented, sometimes showing that a model trained with data of one cuisine performs more or less the same if tested with data of the other cuisine.

With the CRUCUFID dataset instead, we obtained results similar to the ones represented in Figure 1 but less noticeable: the model trained with Western data had only an improvement of 0.13 in the AUC value when tested with Western data with respect to Asian, similarly, the model trained with Asian data had only an improvement of 0.10 in the AUC value. This preliminary work lays the basis for a deeper investigation to understand the role of culture in classification problems.

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